

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

EDUCATING AND RAISING AWARENESS

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Education and raising awareness among the public and Stewards of Trust are essential for fostering trust in science, as they bridge the gap between scientific advancements and societal understanding. VERITY protocol recommendations in this category seek to address scientific complexity, uncertainty, and falsifiability, and explain the iterative nature of scientific progress. They address the ways of countering misconceptions. Other strategies include outreach efforts and awareness campaigns using innovative formats (such as science buses, cafés, and community programs) tailored to cultural and demographic contexts that can build trust in underserved and remote areas. Activities aimed at empowering individuals with digital literacy and critical source evaluation skills can enhance resilience to mis/disinformation and reduce echo chambers by promoting exposure to diverse, credible information sources. Science education and awareness-raising should **not be limited to the general public but extend to all actors in the ecosystem of trust in science**, including policymakers and media, since everyone benefits from understanding the logic of science and scientific methods.

How to support stakeholders and the public's science education and awareness raising?

EDUCATING AND RAISING AWARENESS:

Public Education on Science Fundamentals

- Promote public understanding of the scientific method, including uncertainty, falsifiability, and the iterative process, to counter misconceptions and mistrust.
- Make complex scientific concepts accessible to the public without compromising accuracy.
- Promote public awareness of the economic and social benefits of science, while fostering critical thinking, informed questioning of science-based interventions, and support for responsible research and innovation.

- Offer regular refresher courses for teachers at all educational levels to keep them up to date with current scientific research and responsible research practices to support them in raising informed future citizens.

Curriculum Integration and Innovation

- Incorporate critical thinking, epistemic education (including philosophy of science and citizen science), and media literacy into primary, secondary, and higher education curricula.
- Foster inquiry-based learning, emphasising theory formation, experimentation, and analysis.
- Re-evaluate school curricula to include science ambassadors who can inspire and inform students through school programs.

Targeted and Inclusive Outreach

- Design educational strategies tailored to cultural, demographic, and trust-level differences.
- Use innovative formats like science buses, cafés, and shops to reach underserved communities and remote areas.
- Provide educators and science communicators with tools to address misconceptions and effectively communicate the societal benefits of science.

Bridging Academia, Industry, and Public

- Encourage collaborative projects between academia, industry and civil society to enhance practical education and innovation.
- Clarify how scientists contribute to research, policymaking, and implementation, to show how science supports society.

Combating Mis/Disinformation through Awareness Raising

- Provide targeted digital literacy training for groups like youth and the elderly. Equip individuals with tools to fact-check, verify sources, and evaluate online information critically.
- Encourage exposure to diverse, credible information sources to prevent the formation of echo chambers.

DOWNLOAD VERITY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FOSTERING TRUST IN SCIENCE:

VERITY Recommendations on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16975899>

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Visit VERITY Interactive Tool with all recommendations:

<https://verityproject.eu/verity-recommendations>